

EVOLUTIONARY ANALYSIS OF THEORIES OF CYBERCRIME RISK MANAGEMENT

Khasanov Umidjon Yusupovich

Bukhara State University

independent researcher

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ABSTRACT

Through a systematic analysis of the scientific works of foreign scholars such as A. Hussein [1], A. Ahmed [2], and M. Abdullah [3], which are aimed at examining the stages of development of theories related to public administration within the strategic management of cybercrime risks in economic science and the specific features of each stage, we have established that scientific and theoretical approaches in this area began to take shape after 1960 and have continued to improve structurally across different periods of a six-stage development process.

Through a systematic analysis of the scientific works of foreign scholars such as A. Hussein [1], A. Ahmed [2], and M. Abdullah [3], which are aimed at examining the stages of development of theories related to public administration within the strategic management of cybercrime risks in economic science and the specific features of each stage, we have established that scientific and theoretical approaches in this area began to take shape after 1960 and have continued to improve structurally across different periods of a six-stage development process.

According to the analysis conducted, from the perspective of public administration, the initial foundations of cybercrime risk management theory go back to the early scientific views of the traditional security stage of national security and information protection concepts in 1960–1980. During this period, issues related to “the interpretation of information security in the public administration system mainly from the standpoint of technical and physical protection, and the protection of information resources from external interference with the beginning of the introduction of computer systems into public institutions” [4] came onto the agenda.

By the 1980s, the development of theories of economic and institutional risk management also began to influence the public administration system, which led to the formation of risk management theories for managing cybercrime risks. According to the analysis, we have determined that at this stage, “as risk began to be studied on a scientific basis as a factor of potential loss or uncertainty, approaches aimed at risk identification, assessment, and monitoring became a priority. In particular, the formation of the principle of preliminary assessment of potential threats in public administration decision-making served to create a theoretical basis for managing threats in cyberspace” [5].

In 1995–2005, the global spread of Internet technologies and the introduction of e-government elements into the practices of developed countries radically changed approaches to information security in public administration. Taking into account that during this period “the stage of ensuring the formation of institutional mechanisms for information security management was in effect, and international standards and regulatory systems related to the organization of management in this area were developed” [6], we concluded that this stage can be assessed as the institutionalization stage of information security.

In 2005–2015, cybersecurity emerged as a strategically important priority of national security. During this period, concepts of strategic management of cybercrime risks were formed in the public administration system, and national cybersecurity strategies began to be adopted. According to the analysis, the distinctive feature of this stage is reflected in the fact that “cyber threats were assessed as a strategic factor affecting the stability of public administration, and mechanisms for comprehensive risk assessment, modeling of possible scenarios, and institutional coordination were introduced in public administration systems” [7]. In particular, the development trends of this stage created opportunities to improve the practice of coordinating risks at the level of state policy due to the widespread use of integrated approaches such as “Enterprise Risk Management (ERM)” [8] in the practice of cybercrime risk management. As a result, the mechanism for early detection of cyber threats and strategic decision-making was strengthened. It should be noted that, since the problems of integration and information exchange among state bodies were not fully resolved at this stage, they continued to persist in subsequent periods.

The years 2015–2020 are characterized in the evolution of theories of strategic cybercrime risk management as the stage in which the “Cyber Resilience concept” [9] was formed. The essence of this concept is explained by the fact that “the expansion of digital public administration gives priority not only to protection against cyberattacks, but also to ensuring resilience” [10]. According to the cyber resilience concept, the public administration system should be oriented not toward completely preventing cyberattacks, but toward maintaining its functionality even under attack conditions. Therefore, adaptive management, intelligent monitoring, and dynamic risk assessment mechanisms were introduced into practice. According to the analysis, at this stage, along with prioritizing the expansion of the ability of state systems to adapt to external cyber impacts, measures such as continuous risk monitoring, real-time analysis, and institutional coordination were introduced into public administration practice.

The period after 2020 is assessed as the stage of proactive digital governance in cybercrime risk management, characterized by approaches based on “artificial intelligence and Big Data databases” [11], “machine learning (ML)” [12], and predictive analytics. The introduction of mechanisms for early detection of cyber threats, “automated monitoring” [13], and “predictive governance” [14] in public administration is contributing to the transition of cyber risk management in the public administration system from a reactive model to a proactive and early-warning model. Based on this finding, we considered it appropriate to assess this stage as the stage of proactive digital governance.

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